

FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN LEARNING/TEACHING PROCESS

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Annotation: Formative assessment allows students to be assessed throughout the learning process, and regularly, students work on the feedback they receive and try to improve their knowledge and overcome deficiencies. The purpose of this scientific article is to clarify the importance of formative assessment in the process of teaching and learning the language.

Key words: assessment, learning and teaching process, formative assessment, feedback, skill, method, education system.

INTRODUCTION

The younger generation is always interested in science, so they expect more from what they are learning. This, in turn, requires the teacher to be responsible, well-prepared, technically advanced, competent and, most importantly, evaluative. Education is interpreted as a process of equipping students with knowledge, skills and abilities under the guidance of a teacher, developing their cognitive abilities and shaping their worldview. In addition to educating students in the learning process, regular assessment of students' knowledge is important, and assessment is a key part of the learning process. There are two types of assessment in the learning process: formative and summative. Formative assessment allows for feedback that improves learning, while summative assessment measures learning. Formative assessment is “feedback” for students to

understand what steps they need to take to improve their performance.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

According to Glazer (2014), formative assessment is a generally defined task that allows students to gain feedback on their learning throughout the learning process. In the teaching process, teachers use assessment as a diagnostic tool at the end of the lesson or at the end of the lesson. In addition, teachers can use assessment to teach by identifying students' misconceptions and addressing learning gaps through meaningful feedback. Unfortunately, many educators view formative assessment as a means of measuring students' knowledge. It also loses its ability to assess teacher capacity by not organizing it properly. Testing and teaching may be the same, but approaches to it are different. Assessments are used to determine what children and young people know, understand and are capable of. It is important to monitor this progress, plan next steps, report, and evaluate in order to engage parents, children, and youth in learning. Assessment and feedback are educational and practical aspects that can be found in any field of education. They are factors that can affect each other.

As with many programs in the Middle East (Elebyary, 2013), the current study program focuses too much on the final test and is rarely used to ensure that students receive pre-test preparation strategies. In a study of such programs in Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Libya, Elebyary (2013) found a lack of practice by teachers in foreign language education programs to incorporate group formative assessment into their curricula. Many teachers use formative assessment, such as quizzes or test exams, without fully understanding its application or benefits, and the result may not be as expected. In his academic work, Brown (2005) explored teachers' methods of student assessment, which Brown describes as a development rather than a judgmental practice. The researcher noted that feedback is at the heart of the evaluation process. Formative assessment helps

students learn from their mistakes as well as their correct answers. Quality assimilation is based on quality feedback and emphasizes the importance of timely and regular feedback so that students do not repeat past mistakes.

Glazer (2014) considered assessment to be a key component of the learning process, and it should be fair to all students. For formative assessment to be useful and effective, there must be quality feedback. According to Glazer, quality feedback includes positive feedback as well as areas that need to be improved.

METHODOLOGY

A teacher who changes the lesson a bit can basically predict what the final exam will be like. With this knowledge, the reverse engineering process of the final exam can be done. Dividing the final exam into smaller sections and using them in the form of quizzes in each section of the course will help prepare students for the finals. For unexpected courses, teachers can use past exams for reverse engineering. For courses where the final exam is a secret, teachers can use the course's learning outcomes to manage formative assessment. In most new courses, the final exam is usually an ongoing job, ending a few days before the exam date. Teachers who are eligible to take the final exam can use the test exam to teach their students any unexpected questions that are not covered by the quizzes. This will help students prepare for any blockers that will prevent them from completing a task that quizzes do not cover. This creates a more equal environment where students can test their knowledge fairly.

It should be noted that weekly quizzes cover the entire content of each chapter and allow for positive review as they cover all chapters of the program. Ideally, the goal of any program is to provide students with a balanced teaching and learning experience that can be accomplished through quizzes and quizzes.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Many foreign language teachers focus on assessment at the end of the course,

which is usually in the form of a summative exam, as well as student assessment at the end of the course to provide feedback on the study or fill in gaps in learning. Teachers need to think about how tests support learning and provide opportunities for students to express their opinions, which can then lead to better teaching and learning. Formative assessment allows students to be assessed throughout the program, and on a regular basis, students work on the feedback given to them and improve their knowledge and try to overcome their shortcomings.

The purpose of formative assessment is to help improve the performance of each individual student.

Formative assessment – assessment that promotes learning:

- an element of effective planning, focusing on how students acquire knowledge;
- is a key professional skill of the teacher provides motivation, helps to clarify the goals and criteria;
- helps students understand how to improve their results, develops the ability for self-assessment and mutual assessment;
- reflects all educational achievements;
- should be a permanent element of the lesson.

Formative assessment allows the teacher to:

- clearly formulate the educational result to be assessed in each specific case, and organize their work in accordance with this;
- make the student the subject of educational and evaluation activities;
- can help learn from mistakes;
- can help to understand what is important;
- can help to understand what they are doing;
- can help discover what they don't know;

- can help discover what they can't do.¹

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Researchers have found that negative feedback on evaluations often has a negative impact. Students with low mastery killed their motivation. Black and William (2011) concluded that for formative assessment to be effective, students need to be taught self-assessment. By strengthening students, students can understand what they need to do to achieve. Therefore, it is most important to teach students to use assessment rubrics to help with self-assessment. The assessment shows that teachers can give a brief overview of any learning gaps in the classroom. Teachers can choose retraining or create additional opportunities for students to have more practice in their knowledge. There should be no assessment in formative assessment. Teachers need to focus on giving students meaningful feedback and creating a non-competitive environment. Effects of lesson also based on stages of formative assessment technology.(see table 1)

Table 1.

STAGES OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT TECHNOLOGY	
Step 1	Planning the achievement of educational results of students by topic.
Step 2	Formulation of the goal of the lesson as a condition for achieving the educational results of students' activities.
Step 3	Formulation of the objectives of the lesson as a sequence of steps in the activities of students.
Step 4	Determination of specific criteria for evaluating the activities of students in the lesson.

¹<https://urok.1sept.ru/articles/677370#:~:text=>

Step 5	Evaluation of students' activities in accordance with the criteria.
Step 6	Implementation of feedback (from teacher to student, from student to student, from student to student).
Step 7	Comparison of students' results with the previous level of their achievements.
Step 8	Determining the student's place on the path to achieving the goal.
Step 9	Correction of the educational route of the student.

There are five Principles of Formative Assessment

- The teacher regularly provides feedback by providing students with comments, remarks, etc. about their activities.
- Students take an active part in organizing their own learning process.
- The teacher changes teaching techniques and technologies depending on the change in the learning outcomes of students.
- The teacher is aware that assessment through a mark sharply reduces the motivation and self-esteem of students.
- The teacher recognizes the need to teach students the principles of self-assessment and ways to improve their own performance.

Formative assessment is based on criteria and benchmarks. The criteria-based assessment system should enable:

- determine how successfully a particular educational material was mastered,
- determine whether a particular practical skill has been formed,
- check the level achieved by the student, laid down in the learning task (a set of learning tasks).²

An example of this is to comment on a speech exercise and ask students to apply feedback and complete the speech exercise a second time. The same can be done

² <https://urok.1sept.ru/articles/677370#:~:text=>

for formative assessment, where students can apply their feedback and submit for a second assessment. Another suggestion is to use the rubric to guide students on performance criteria based on a number of assessments. This is especially useful when students identify their peers using a rubric. This helps students to carefully consider the assessment criteria and facilitates self-regulatory learning.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, there are a number of factors that affect students' success in high-level exams, many of which cannot be measured. Some of these factors may include class attendance, student engagement level, appropriate student placement, time spent studying, and the effectiveness of different feedback. However, some assessments, such as the use of quizzes and test exams, can be analyzed to identify patterns or characteristics that can predict success.

Teachers can use formative assessment in many ways to help students complete summative assignments. Using well-designed formative assessments to prepare for the final assessment will be one of the approaches in education. Well-designed assessment assignments should include quality questions that allow for feedback. Formative assessment encourages students to review lesson material and think critically about what has been covered in the lesson.

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